

Preliminary Descriptive Analysis of Metadata Elements in selected UK Longitudinal Population Study Platforms

Jon Johnson (CLOSER, Institute of Education, UCL) ORCID: 0000-0001-5085-3296
Steve McEachern (UK Data Service, University of Essex) ORCID: 0000-0001-7848-4912

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Platform selection

In the process of constructing a proposal for the Population Research UK call “Searchable register and UK Longitudinal Population Study (LPS) information hub”

<https://pruk.ac.uk/searchable-register-and-information-hub/>, we conducted a desk based analysis of ten platforms, six named in the call specification (*italicised below*) and a further four which are providers of comparable information for other widely used UK longitudinal population studies.

These selected platforms are:

- *Atlas of Longitudinal Datasets*
- *CLOSER Discovery*
- *Dementia Platforms UK*
- *Health Data Research Gateway*
- *UKDS Data Catalogue*
- *UK-LLC Data Explorer*
- Biobank
- CALLS-HUB
- Gateway to Global Aging
- MetadataWorks platforms

Appendix A lists the websites and selection criteria for studies which are held on the platform included in the analysis.

Studies by platform

Table 1, shows the number of studies available on each platform. The total is less than the sum of each platform as studies are available on multiple platforms. Supporting data is available in the accompanying data file at Appendix D.

Table 1: Number of studies by platform

Platform	No. of Studies
Atlas of Longitudinal Datasets	64
Biobank	1
Dementia Platform UK	16
Metadata Works	10
CALLS HUB	3
Gateway to Global Aging	2
HDR-UK	8
UKLLC	21
CLOSER	13
UKDS	16
Total number of studies	72

Table 2: Number of platforms on which study is available

Occurrence of Study	No. of Studies
1	28
2	24
3	8
4	7
5	4
6	1
Total number of studies	72

Metadata elements

Metadata elements identified for this analysis are those used to support a high level catalogue and those to support variable and question search.

Catalogue metadata

A study catalogue is intended to give a user an overview of the key common characteristics of a study and the resources associated with the study itself including documentation, data dictionaries, access information.

There is no standard set of catalogue elements in widespread usage other than Dublin Core¹ which covers basic discovery to support any study catalogue and most often used as a standard sub-set of elements within other standards. Often as the individual fields relate to the domain in which the study takes place additional fields are added. Within the domains within which LPS resides, the DCAT², DCAT-AP³ and DDI⁴ standards which both contain Dublin Core 1.1 are widely deployed.

PRUK have carried out some initial consultation⁵ within the LPS community on domain specific fields.

We have used the twenty seven fields identified in this report and mapped them to the 10 platforms (Appendix B). The absence / presence is measured by the field appearing at all, as a single metadata element, e.g. concatenating two metadata elements in the same field would be indicated by a 0.

Table 3 summarises the distribution of catalogue fields by platform. Information represented by the fields may appear elsewhere on the platforms, in textual description.

¹ <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-terms/>

² <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/>

³ <https://op.europa.eu/en/web/eu-vocabularies/dcat-ap>

⁴ https://ddialliance.org/product_overview

⁵ Boyd, A., Katharine, E., & Orton, C. (2025). Workshop report: Designing a sustainable study profile metadata portal. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16965949>

Table 3: Number of available catalogue metadata fields by platform

Platform	No. of fields
Atlas of Longitudinal Datasets	11
Biobank	1
Dementia Platform UK	12
Metadata Works	10
CALLS HUB	6
Gateway to Global Aging	1
HDR-UK	11
UKLLC	8
CLOSER	11
UKDS	3
Number of fields	27

Variable & question metadata

Nine metadata elements were chosen for comparison, to assess the commonalities and differences in variable and question / measurement metadata to support a viable and useful searchable register. Availability of a vocabulary or structured topic organisation was also captured. Availability of an API is also recorded. .

Appendix C: shows for each metadata element, availability on each platform. This is summarised in Tables 4 and 5 below.

Table 4: Summary of variable and question metadata elements

Metadata Field	Count of platforms	Number of studies	Studies via API
Variable Name	8	48	34
Variable label	8	48	34
Variable code list	5	39	28
Valid Cases	2	27	26
Questionnaire description	5	21	21
Questionnaire	1	15	15
Questions text	2	21	21
Response domain	1	15	15
Topics	5	21	27
Total	10	72	72

APIs

An API allows potential automation of metadata retrieval. We classified platforms by type of API. To help understand the potential for use of an API as a mechanism to harvest metadata (as listed in Table 5), the classification gives an indication of the number of API endpoints to be supported and the number of studies able to be retrieved.

Table 5: Summary of availability of API and available number of items harvestable

Availability	No. of platforms	Unique studies	Min/max No. metadata items
Open API (DDI)	2	21	7/9
Open API (bespoke)	2	9	2/5
API (bespoke - not accessible)	3	11	2/5
No API	3	31	0/0
Total	10	72	9

Appendix A: Data Sources

Platform	URLs	No. Studies	Notes
Atlas of Longitudinal Datasets	https://atlaslongitudinaldatasets.ac.uk/explore	64	Selection criteria, UK and accessible via study website, data sharing platform etc.
Biobank	https://biobank.ndph.ox.ac.uk/showcase/	1	
Dementia Platforms UK	https://data.dpuk.ukserp.ac.uk/cohortdirectory	16	
MetadataWorks platforms	https://www.adruk.org/data-access/data-catalogue/ https://ons.metadata.works/browser/landing https://rds.metadata.works	10	Search for datasets with Longitudinal data
CELSIUS	https://calls.ac.uk/variables/	3	
Gateway to Global Aging	https://g2aging.org/health-and-retirement-studies/overview	2	
Health Data Research Gateway	https://healthdatagateway.org/en/search?type=datasets&isCohortDiscovery=&page=1&query=longitudinal	8	Studies with data variables
UK-LLC	https://explore.ukllc.ac.uk	21	Exclude linkage datasets
CLOSER	https://discovery.closer.ac.uk	13	
UKDS	https://datacatalogue.ukdataservice.ac.uk	16	Series, examined for LPS in UK

Appendix B: Available Metadata Elements (Catalogue)

Metadata Field	Atlas	Biobank	Dementia Platforms	Metadata Works	LS studies	Gateway to Global Aging	HDR-UK	UKLLC	CLOSER	UKDS	Total
LPS name	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	9
LPS acronym	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	4
LPS logo	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	3
LPS website	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	3
LPS contact email	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Data Controller's name	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	4
Principal Investigator	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2
Funder	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2
Summary of LPS	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	8
LPS keywords/tags	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
Geographic coverage	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	5
Size of cohort	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	4
Recruitment dates to cohort	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	5
Age range	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Age at recruitment	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2
Start date of data collection	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	4
End date of data collection	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	4
Length of follow-up	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
How data were collected	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2

Why data were collected	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Links to LPS documentation	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Link to data dictionary	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Access requirements	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	3
Access process	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Access environment	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
How many times followed up?	0	0	1		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Is the study still recruiting?	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Count	11	1	12	10	6	0	11	8	11	3	-	

Appendix C: Available Metadata Elements (Variable & Question)

Metadata Field	Atlas of Longitudinal Datasets	Biobank ¹	Dementia Platform UK ²	Metadata Works ³	CALLS HUB ⁴	Gateway to Global Aging ⁵	HDR-UK	UKLLC	CLOSER	UKDS	Count
API	Not accessible	Bespoke	Not accessible	Not accessible	No	No	Bespoke	No	Yes	Yes	4
Instrument description	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	5
Instrument	No	Image	No	No	PDF	Popup	No	No	Yes	No	1
Questions text	No	Image	No	No	PDF	Popup	No	No	Yes	Yes	2
Response domain	No	Image	No	No	PDF	Popup	No	No	Yes	No	1
Variable Name	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Popup	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	8
Variable label	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Popup	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	8
Variable code list	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Popup	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	5
Valid Cases	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	2
Topics	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	5

¹ Instrument, question text and response domain presence, as image

² API exists but no documentation

³ API exists but no documentation

⁴ Instrument, question text and response domain presence, as PDF

⁵ Variable and question information present, as popup

Appendix D: Study Coverage by Platform

See accompanying file UKLPS Metadata Landscape.xlsx